

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators celebrates a year of joint work on strategies in Science in Hungary

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Furthermore, the project aims to develop structured support programs aimed at enabling scientific communities to fully embrace Open Science, Open Innovation, Open Education, Engaged Science and Engaged Education.

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project aims to transform the region into a hub of excellence in Research and Innovation.

On the 5th and 6th of October 2023, the six founding countries of the European University E³UDRES² met at the Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences, in Hungary, to celebrate and discuss the first year of joint work within the scope of the project E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators.

This event marks a year of collaborative efforts to develop joint research and innovation strategies. Among the objectives of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project is the co-creation of a common strategy and agenda to accelerate the transformation of the region into a European Research and Innovation Center for Smart and Sustainable Regions.

One of the main focuses of the E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators project is to achieve equitable conditions in terms of institutional Human Resources for Research strategies and policies. This involves addressing significant challenges, such as implementing new career assessments and joint recruitment strategies.

Another crucial goal is the development of a structured and integrated framework to harmoniously connect all Research and Innovation ecosystems and the knowledge triangle of the E³UDRES² alliance, which encompasses education, research and innovation. The project actively promotes dialogue with other similar alliances, Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), HEI associations and political decision-makers.

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators

project objectives

Objective 1: Co-create a common strategy and agenda that unlocks our potential for excellence in Research and Innovation, to accelerate the transformation into a multi-institutional European Research and Innovation Centre for Smart and Sustainable Regions

Objective 2: Develop best practices and a strategy for pooling Research infrastructures, expertise, data and resources and for collaborating with/getting access to other strategic research infrastructures

Objective 3: Develop structured support programmes aimed at empowering our scientific communities to fully embrace Open Science (OS), Open Innovation (OI), Open Education (OE), Engaged Science and Engaged Education

Objective 4: Work to achieve a level playing field in terms of institutional strategies and policies for Human Resources for Research, from which we will be able to address bigger challenges, such as brain mobility, new career assessments and joint recruitment strategies

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Objective 5: Develop a structured and integrated framework to seamlessly link all our R&I ecosystems and the E³UDRES² alliance's knowledge triangle of education, Research and Innovation

Objective 6: Along our pathway to build a common R&I agenda, be connected and dialogue with peer Alliances and Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), HEI associations and advocacy groups, and policy-makers with a view to contribute with evidence-based results to the co-creation of future EEA/ERA (European Education Area/European Research Area) work programmes and to inform better policies

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(...) THE E³UDRES²
ALLIANCE'S KNOWLEDGE
TRIANGLE OF
EDUCATION, RESEARCH
AND INNOVATION

BETTER Life Starts to Make a Better Life

(E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators cluster project)

It is not easy to communicate the project which deals with socially engaged research. It is even more difficult when such communication concerning science is one of the essential pillars of socially engaged research in life sciences. However, the wording and acronym of the project **BETTER Life** perfectly suits this intention. The project by its full name “**Bringing Excellence to Transformative Engaged Research in Life Sciences through Integrated Digital Centres**” underscores its primary goal: establishing an inter-institutional support structure dedicated to enhancing the capabilities of early career researchers.

BETTER Life

www.betterlifehorizon.eu

BRINGING EXCELLENCE TO TRANSFORMATIVE ENGAGED RESEARCH IN LIFE SCIENCES THROUGH INTEGRATED DIGITAL CENTRES

- Strategic Planning**

To consolidate a strategic vision for the EU BETTER Life Digital Centre committed to long-term sustainability.
- Development of Tools**

To build intra- and inter-institutional capacities to foster societally engaged research in life sciences through diverse tools.
- Capacity Building**

To develop the individual capacities of early career researchers for implementing socially engaged research in life sciences.
- Finetuning and Sustaining**

To consolidate the EU BETTER Life Centre as a reference for socially engaged research in life sciences.

The BETTER Life project is establishing the European **Digital Centre of Excellence** for Socially Engaged Research in Life Sciences together with seven local digital centres, which will help early career researchers **boost social engagement** in their research and will contribute to tackling societal challenges in diverse regional ecosystems.

Socially Engaged Research in the field of life sciences serves as the cornerstone for forging connections among **research, government, industry, civil society, and the environment**, embodying the innovative concept of the **quadruple helix model**. Strengthening the capabilities to foster socially engaged science will not only enhance the influence of life science research but also facilitate the alignment of researchers with the demands of their surrounding ecosystems.

For more information, please visit the official [BETTER Life \(betterlifehorizon.eu\)](https://www.betterlifehorizon.eu) website, and follow us on [LinkedIn](#), [Facebook](#) and [X \(Twitter\)](#). Stay engaged with BETTER Life!

Patrik Toula, BETTER Life Project Coordinator (Czech University of Life Sciences Prague)

The EXPER Project: Elevating Regional Innovation and Excellence in Widening Universities

(E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-novators cluster project)

Universities serve as central hubs within regional innovation systems, bridging academic and business interests while facilitating international connections. To effectively fulfil these roles, universities must undergo institutional transformations. European funding programmes emphasise cooperation as a catalyst for mutual learning, innovation, and excellence, promoting efficient resource utilisation and a broader impact through international collaboration.

Despite advancements in virtual communication, geographical proximity remains vital for effective cooperation. Universities in Outermost Regions (ORs) like the Azores and Canary Islands face challenges due to their distance from renowned higher education institutions. However, these regions possess unique attributes, such as biodiversity, renewable energy resources, and strategic locations, making them valuable research and innovation hubs.

To harness their regional strengths, collaboration with leading European and international research networks is essential.

[‘Excellent Peripheries for a Strong European Research Area’ \(EXPER\)](#) aims to facilitate such partnerships, fostering mutual learning and competence building within a network of higher education institutions and local partners. [EXPER](#) also focuses on enhancing scientific excellence and innovation capacity in green and blue research domains. This includes developing institutional transformation plans aligned with research and innovation strategies, emphasising interdisciplinary approaches to tackle societal challenges in these economies.

Specifically, the project targets the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC) and the University of the Azores (UAC) through capacity-building activities and international cooperation with universities like the University of Rostock (UROS) and the University of Calabria (UNICAL). Key project objectives include elevating the universities' excellence profiles, planning their institutional transformation, organising capacity-building activities, and laying the foundation for a European University Alliance. [EXPER](#) adopts a community-based approach, involving ecosystem representatives in shaping a modernization strategy for expanding universities. By enhancing scientific excellence and innovation capacity, these universities are poised to drive economic and social transformation in their respective regions.

Víctor Ricardo Martínez. Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation, Spain.

30 October 23

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-Novators video series

The first three videos of the series of 9 videos that we will have to develop throughout the project are available on our YouTube channel. These videos present testimonies of the work carried out by WP2, WP3 and WP4 in the first year of the project. <https://www.youtube.com/@entrenovators>

29 September 23

European Researchers' Night

E³UDRES² Ent-r-e-Novators was present at the exhibitions at the various events included in the European Researchers' Night held by IPS, MATE, STPUAS and Via. This presence aims to increase the notoriety of the project and its objectives among targets inside and outside the institutions of the EUDRES Alliance

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